

OPERAS-P

OPEN SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION IN THE EUROPEAN
RESEARCH AREA FOR SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES -
PREPARATION

Communication, Outreach and Advocacy

OPERAS-P Portal created

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OPEN SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION IN SSH IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA - PREPARATION

Deliverable [identifier] **OPERAS-P Portal Created**

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I. Executive summary

This deliverable describes the creation of a new OPERAS portal and includes a structure of this new portal. The previous website of the infrastructure OPERAS will be transformed to be used as a blog hosted on "Hypotheses", a platform for humanities and social science research blogs (<https://hypotheses.org/>) run by OpenEdition.

II. Portal

The University of Turin has created a new OPERAS page that will serve as an OPERAS portal in future, based on WordPress. The University of Turin will host the OPERAS website.

<https://www.operas.unito.it/>

The structure for the new website is prepared. A decision for the new structure was made in the OPERAS-P WP7 meeting on November 7, 2019. The structure will be adapted regularly.

A. Menu structure of the OPERAS portal

1. OPERAS Logo (Link to starting page)

2. About

A. About OPERAS (Mission - Vision - Values)

a. OPERAS in a nutshell

b. OPERAS legal entity (funded and legal status)

c. OPERAS and Open Science

i. OPERAS and Open Scholarly Communication (rooted in the ecosystem)

ii. OPERAS and EOSC (more technical)

B. Governance schema

a. **Members** (this explains our governance structure and lists all members of the core group as well as the ordinary members and partners, the menu bar on the left side should include a filter according to countries)

- b. **Coordination Team** (provide information on OCT with contacts and also explain that we are the member support)
 - c. **National Nodes/National Coordinators**
 - d. —> in future: Different Assemblies ...
- C. Info material** (this is where you can download logos, blank presentations etc. and where OPERAS makes available the material of our Zenodo community and any other relevant documents, it should include a filter for the different stakeholders: librarians, researchers, publishers, infrastructures)
- D. How we work together** (Policy document)

3. Want to Know More

- A. Want to Join/Get involved**
- a. **Become a member** (explanation of how organizations can join, what we expect, whom to contact from your country)
 - b. **Become a partner** (how you can cooperate as an ERIC or infrastructure)
 - c. **Rules of engagements**
 - d. **National Nodes** (different presentation of the core group, as national contacts, less institutions, but persons to contact)
- B. News (OPERAS Blog)** (link to OPERAS Blog: hypotheses.operas.org, open a new tab)
- C. Events** (show next events with calendar like on “Home”)
- a. **Filter** (according to the type of event and country)
 - b. **Past events**

4. Special Interest Groups (what are OPERAS Special Interest Groups)

- A. **Advocacy**
- B. **Best Practices**
- C. **Common Standards**
- D. **Multilingualism**
- E. **OA Business Models**
- F. **Platforms and Services**
- G. **Tools R&D**

5. Services (page with all services listed; if there is a service we link directly to the service, in the meantime we will have an information page)

- A. **Discovery Service (TRIPLE)**
- B. **Metrics Service**

- C. **Certification Service (DOAB)**
- D. **Publishing Service Portal (PSP)**
- E. **Research for Society**
- F. **Future Services**

6. **Projects** (page with a list of all projects and with info on how they are linked to OPERAS)

- A. **OPERAS-P** (info about the project including requirements like deliverables)
- B. **TRIPLE** (info about the project including requirements like deliverables)
- C. **SSHOC**
 - a. (maybe more linked projects)
- D. **Past projects**

7. **International Partnerships** (opening page with all networks and connections explained)

- A. **CO-OPERAS** (manifesto, members, link to the GoFair webpage)
- B. **OABook Network** (link to slack)
- C. **IOI** (link to the website)
- D. **In All languages** (link to the website)
- E. **ENRESSH** (link to the website)

8. Search bar

B. Structure of the front page

- 1. **Social media buttons**
- 2. **Slider with the banner**
- 3. **Icons**
 - A. **OPERAS: How to** (About OPERAS)
 - B. **Voices from the community** (videos)
 - C. **Services**
 - D. **Bookshelf** (Zotero Community)
 - E. **Need more?**
 - F. **Work with us/Contact**

4. **Calendar** (show calendar on the left side, on right side show next event)
5. **Twitter** (left side) and **Blog posts** (right side)

Footer:

1. **Imprint**
2. **Terms of Use**
3. **Data privacy statement**
4. **Contact**
5. **Funding information as required by European Commission**

III. Relocation Plan

The relocation of the OPERAS website will take place in several different steps. First, the pages will be copied to the new portal, and new pages as needed for the portal will be added. After this process is finished, the url [operas-eu.org](https://www.operas-eu.org) will be redirected to the UniTo website <https://www.operas.unito.it/>. Only the blog posts will remain at the hypotheses blog. The permalinks of the blog posts will redirect the user to the hypotheses blog. After the website migration, the blog at hypotheses will be restructured.

IV. Blog

Currently, the blog at hypotheses <https://operas.hypotheses.org/> is used as a website. After the implementation of the new portal at Unito, the current website will be kept as a blog where all OPERAS-related news are announced and detailed topic-specific articles are published. The blog will be restructured to offer different blog series. Ideas for new series are:

- OPERAS News
- OPERAS Community (Report on interesting events and happenings in the community)
- OPERAS Behind the Scenes (Introducing people working for OPERAS, developing services ...)

V. Dissemination level

PU = Public

